

Terpenoids : Part LVII. Syntheses of β -Farnesene and Methylene Isomer of Tagetol

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β -Farnesene and methylene isomer of tagetol have been synthesised through Wittig reaction on suitably positioned ketones.

3-substituted-1, 3-butadiene system is a characteristic structural feature of many terpenoids. As a part of our investigations towards the syntheses of various terpenoids²⁻⁴ through Wittig reaction¹, we have developed a convenient and general method for the elaboration of 3-substituted-1,3-butadiene system. The syntheses of title compounds by the application of the new approach are being reported in this communication.

β -Farnesene, an acyclic terpenoid was isolated from the sesquiterpene fraction of oil of hops⁵. It has been assigned constitution (I) on the basis of chemical reactions and spectroscopic studies^{5,6}.

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In the absence of any previously reported direct synthesis of the compound, the present studies provide confirmatory evidence in support of the structure (I). Scheme of the synthesis proceeds as follows :

Ethyl 5,9-dimethyl-2-carbethoxy-4,8-decadien-1-oate (II), the starting material was prepared according to Barnard and Bateman⁷. One of the carbethoxy groups of the substituted malonic ester (II) was eliminated by refluxing it with sodium cyanide in dimethylsulphoxide⁸ to afford ethyl 5,9-dimethyl-4,8-decadien-1-oate (III) which was smoothly reduced to the corresponding carbinol (IV) with lithium aluminium hydride. Oxidation of the alcohol (IV) with excess of *Collin's* reagent⁹ provided 5,9-dimethyl-4,8-decadien-1-al (V) in excellent yield after chromatography over alumina. The aldehyde was submitted to the action of vinyl magnesium bromide in tetrahydrofuran to furnish, 7,11-dimethyl-1,6,10-dodecatrien-3-ol (VI) which was subsequently oxidised with *Jones* reagent to give α - β -unsaturated ketone(VII). This ketone, after purification by chromatography, was finally subjected to Wittig reaction with methylenetriphenylphosphorane to form β -farnesene which was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina (elution with pet. ether, 40–60°) followed by vacuum distillation. The identity of purified synthetic product with the natural β -farnesene was established by comparison of I.R. and U.V. spectral data¹⁰.

Methylene isomer of tagetol was isolated, from frass produced by *IPs confusus* feeding in *ponderosa* pine¹¹. Formulation (VIII) proposed for it on the basis of spectral data¹¹ has been recently confirmed through a synthesis.¹²

For accomplishing the present synthesis of the title compound, we required 5-methyl-3,3-ethylenedioxy-hexanal (XII) as the key intermediate for elaboration to the desired

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3-substituted-1,3-butadiene system. This aldehyde (XII) was made available by the carbethoxylation of isobutyl methyl ketone according to Soloway *et al.*¹³ The carbonyl function in (IX) was protected by ketalisation with ethylene glycol in benzene in the presence of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid. Reduction of ketal ester (X) with lithium aluminium hydride furnished the corresponding carbinal (XI) which was subsequently oxidised with excess of Collins reagent⁹ to yield 5-methyl-3 ; 3-ethylenedioxy-hexanal (XII) in 82% yield after chromatography over alumina. The ketal aldehyde thus obtained was tailored to the final product through a series of unambiguous and well-known reactions. Grignard reaction of vinyl magnesium bromide on (XII) generated 7-methyl-5,5-ethylenedioxy-1-octen-3-ol (XIII) in quantitative yield. Oxidation of the allylic alcohol (XIII) with Jones reagent followed by chromatography over alumina gave α , β -unsaturated ketone (XIV). Wittig reaction¹ of (XIV) with methylene-triphenyl-phosphorane resulted in the formation of the desired diene (XV). This was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina. De-ketalisation of the ketal (XV) under mild conditions afforded 2-methyl-6-methylene-7-octen-4-one (XVI) in 63% yield after repeated careful fractionations. Identity of the ketone (XVI) was established through the comparison of its I.R. spectrum with that reported in literature¹². The above ketone was transformed into methylene isomer of tagetol by reduction with sodium borohydride. I.R. and U.V. spectrum of the synthesised product were in good agreement with those of the natural sample¹¹.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Ethyl 5,9-dimethyl-4,8-decadien-1-oate (III): A mixture of diester (II, 60 g.), dimethylsulphoxide (80 ml.) and sodium cyanide (20 g.) was heated at 160–70° for 4 hours. Thereafter, the mixture was cooled, poured into cold water and extracted thrice with petroleum ether (40–60°). The combined extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent expelled. The residue, upon distillation under reduced pressure, furnished (36 g., 80%) of the monoester (III); b.p. 120–25°/10 mm; η_D^{32} 1.4950.

(Found: C, 74.68; H, 10.71. $C_{14}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 74.95; H, 10.78%). Infra red spectrum showed characteristic bands at 1740 cm^{-1} (ester); 830, 785 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted double bond).

5,9-Dimethyl-4,8-decadien-1-ol (IV): To a fine suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (3.2 g.) in dry ether (250 ml.) was added dropwise with stirring the above ester (III, 35 g.) in anhydrous ether (150 ml.) so as to keep the ether at a gentle reflux. After the reaction mixture had been stirred for another 3 hrs, it was cooled and poured into ice-cold saturated solution of sodium sulphate. The product was extracted with ether and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation afforded the alcohol (IV); b.p. 125°/10 mm; yield 23 g. (80%); η_D^{32} 1.4710.

(Found: C, 78.84; H, 12.33. $C_{12}H_{22}O$ requires C, 79.06; H, 12.16%). I.R. spectrum showed no absorption in carbonyl region but had characteristic bands at 3400, 1050 cm^{-1} (–OH); 825, 785 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted double bond).

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* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalysis was done by Mr. B. N. Anand, Panjab University, Chemistry Department, Chandigarh. I.R. Spectra were recorded on Beckmann I R-5 with sodium chloride optics using thin liquid films.

5,9-Dimethyl-4,8-decadien-1-ol (V): Chromium trioxide (68 g.) was added in small instalments to well cooled anhydrous pyridine (680 ml.) with stirring. The contents were stirred further for 15 minutes after which the complex formed was separated by washing and decantation with petroleum ether (40–60°). The yellow brownish complex was dissolved in dry methylene chloride (750 ml.) and to this was added the alcohol (IV, 20 g.). After stirring for 15 minutes at 25°, the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water (300 ml.) and the organic layer separated. It was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated to remove the solvent. The residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (40–60°)-benzene mixture (4 : 1) as eluent. The product obtained was subsequently distilled under reduced pressure to give (16.4 g., 83%) of the pure aldehyde (V); b.p. 105.9°/10 mm; η_D^{32} 1.4760.

(Found : C, 79.81; H, 11.06. $C_{12}H_{20}O$ requires C, 79.94; H, 11.18%). The aldehyde was characterised by its infra red spectrum which showed characteristic peaks at 1705, 2705 cm^{-1} (–CHO); 820, 785 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted double bond). There was no absorption in the –OH region.

7,11-Dimethyl-1,6,10-dodecatrien-3-ol (VI): Grignard reagent was prepared from magnesium (3.0 g.) and vinyl bromide (14.0 g.) in 60 ml. of dry T.H.F. To this was added the aldehyde (V, 15 g.) in dry T.H.F. (50 ml.) dropwise and with constant stirring. After the addition was over, the contents were left overnight at room temperature and, thereafter, the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for about 4 hrs to complete the reaction. The cooled contents were decomposed with saturated solution of ammonium chloride and worked up in the usual manner to obtain the allylic alcohol (VI); b.p. 130–35°/10 mm; yield 13.5 g (77%); η_D^{32} 1.4755.

(Found : C, 80.57; H, 11.52. $C_{14}H_{24}O$ requires C, 80.71; H, 11.61%). I.R. spectrum did not show any absorption in the carbonyl region but exhibited characteristic bands at 3350, 1045 cm^{-1} (–OH); 3050, 1645, 980, 910 cm^{-1} (vinylic double bond).

7,11-Dimethyl-1,6,10-dodecatrien-3-one (VII): Jones' reagent (13.5 ml.) was added, in small portions at a time, to an ice-cold solution of the alcohol (VII, 10 g.) in acetone (100 ml.). The mixture was stirred for half an hour, decomposed with sodium bicarbonate solution and extracted with ether. The combined extract was washed with water, 5% solution of sodium bicarbonate and again with water. The residue left after the removal of solvent was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (40–60°)-benzene mixture (1 : 4) as eluent. Vacuum distillation of the product afforded (5.1 g, 51%) of the ketone (VII) b.p. 115°/10 mm; η_D^{32} 1.4901.

(Found : C, 80.9; H, 10.63. $C_{14}H_{22}O$ requires C, 81.5; H, 10.75%). I.R. spectrum was marked by the absence of any absorption in the –OH region. There were characteristic bands at 1690 cm^{-1} (conj. carbonyl); 3050, 1650, 915 cm^{-1} (–CH = CH₂).

7,11-Dimethyl-3-methylene-1,6,10-dodecatrien (I): Methylene-phosphorane was prepared under nitrogen atmosphere from sodium hydride (0.51 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (10.5 ml.) and methyl triphenyl phosphonium iodide (8.5 g.) in the usual way. To this was added the ketone (VII, 4.0 g.) in dry T.H.F. (10 ml.). The contents were stirred and heated

for 1 hour at 50° and left overnight. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water (100 ml.) and extracted with petroleum ether (40–60°). After drying and solvent removal, the residue was chromatographed through neutral alumina, column, when elution with petroleum ether (40–60°, 60 ml.) afforded the pure compound (I). It was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure to obtain the final product; b.p. 95–107°/3–4 mm; yield 2.9 g. (72.3%), η_D^{32} 1.4780 (Literature⁶ reports b.p. 75–90°/0.9 mm.).

(Found : C, 88.23; H, 11.75; Calc'd for $C_{15}H_{24}$: C, 88.16; H, 11.84%). I.R. spectrum had peaks at 3090, 2850, 1600, 1400, 1350, 998, 905, 888, 820, 800 cm^{-1} which are closely comparable to those reported in the literature. U.V. spectrum had $\lambda_{max}^{methanol} = 223 m\mu$ ($\epsilon \sim 20,000$).

Ethyl 5-methyl-3,3-ethylenedioxy hexanoate (X) : A mixture of keto-ester (IX, 25 g.), prepared according to the procedure described in literature, ethylene glycol (10 ml.), anhydrous benzene (200 ml.) and *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (100 mg.) was refluxed under a continuous water separator for 6 hours at 120°. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature, neutralised with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and worked up in the usual manner when 28.8 g. (92%) of the ketal ester distilled over at 110–115°/10 mm; η_D^{32} 1.4590. The compound did not produce any violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

(Found : C, 60.82; H, 9.23. $C_{11}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 61.09; H, 9.32%). Infra red spectrum showed characteristic bands at 1740 cm^{-1} (ester); 1030, 1070 cm^{-1} (ketal).

5-Methyl-3,3-ethylenedioxy-hexanol (XI) : The above ketal ester (X, 32 g.) in dry ether (150 ml.) was added dropwise to a well-stirred suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (3.0 g.) in dry ether (250 ml.). The contents were further stirred for 3 hrs. cooled, decomposed with well-cooled saturated solution of sodium sulphate and worked up in the usual way to afford the alcohol (XI); b.p. 115°/10 mm; yield 20 g. (78%); η_D^{32} 1.4430.

(Found : C, 61.52; H, 10.19. $C_9H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 62.04; H, 10.41%). I.R. spectrum did not show any absorption in the carbonyl region but had characteristic bands at 3400 cm^{-1} (–OH), 1020–1070 cm^{-1} (ketal and alcohol).

5-Methyl-3,3-ethylene dioxy-hexanal (XII) : The alcohol (XI, 19 g.) was oxidised with the complex obtained from chromium trioxide (67 g.) and pyridine (670 ml.) in the manner described under (V) to afford (15.5 g., 82%) of 5-methyl-3,3-ethylenedioxy-hexanal (XII) after chromatography over neutral alumina (using petroleum ether-benzene mixture (4 : 1) for elution) followed by vacuum distillation; b.p. 120°/12 mm; η_D^{32} 1.4475.

(Found : C, 62.59; H, 9.31. $C_9H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 62.76; H, 9.36%). Infra red spectrum showed characteristic bands at 2710, 1710 cm^{-1} (–CHO); 1040, 1060 cm^{-1} (ketal), but had no absorption in the –OH region.

7-Methyl-5,5-ethylenedioxy-1-octen-3-ol (XIII) : To the Grignard reagent, prepared from magnesium (3.2 g.) and vinyl bromide (14.5 g.) in dry T.H.F. (100 ml.) was added dropwise and with stirring the ketal aldehyde (XII, 15 g.) in dry T.H.F. (50 ml.). After allowing to stand overnight, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hours on a water bath. It was

then cooled, decomposed with saturated ammonium chloride solution and worked up in the usual way to furnish the allylic alcohol (XIII); b.p. 142–48°/10 mm; yield 13.5 g. (78%); η_D^{32} 1.4574.

(Found : C, 65.78; H, 9.96. $C_{11}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 65.97; H, 10.07%) Infra red spectrum showed no absorption bands in the carbonyl region; characteristic peaks at 3400 cm^{-1} (–OH); 1020–1070 cm^{-1} (ketal and alcoholic); 3030, 1635, 980, 915 cm^{-1} (–CH = CH₂).

7-Methyl-5,5-ethylenedioxy-1-octen-3-one (XIV) : The allylic alcohol (XIII, 12 g.) in acetone (75 ml.) was oxidised with Jones's reagent (16.2 ml.) at 0° and worked up in the usual manner. The residue left after the removal of solvent was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina when elution with 20% benzene-petroleum ether (40–60°) mixture gave the pure ketal ketone (XIV). It was further purified by distillation under vacuum; b.p. 112°/10 mm; yield 6.3 g. (51.5%); η_D^{32} 1.4490.

(Found : C, 66.31; H, 8.91. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.64; H, 9.15%). Infra red spectrum had characteristic bands at 1685 cm^{-1} (conj. carbonyl); 1070 cm^{-1} (ketal); 3045, 1630, 980, 915 cm^{-1} (–CH = CH₂). There was no absorption in the –OH region.

7-Methyl-5,5-ethylenedioxy-3-methylene-1-octen (XV) : To the methylene phosphorane, obtained from sodium hydride (0.65 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (13.7 ml.) and methyl triphenyl phosphonium iodide (11 g.) in dimethylsulphoxide (27.4 ml.), was added the above ketone (XIV, 5 g.) in dry T.H.F. (10 ml.) at room temperature. The contents were stirred for 1 hr at 50°, left overnight and then worked up as usual. Removal of the solvent, chromatography over neutral alumina (elution with 40–60° petroleum ether) and vacuum distillation afforded (3.6 g., 72%) of (XV); b.p. 105°/8 mm; η_D^{32} 1.4510.

(Found : C, 72.87; H, 10.16. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 73.43; H, 10.27%). Infra red spectrum showed the absence of carbonyl group. It had characteristic bands at 3050 cm^{-1} (olefinic double bond), 1610 cm^{-1} (conj. double bond), 995 and 905 cm^{-1} (vinyl), 1070 cm^{-1} (ketal).

2-Methyl-6-methylene-7-octen-4-one (XVI) : To the preceding ketal diene (XV, 3 g.) were added acetone (75 ml.), *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (1 g.) and water (10 ml.) and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 hour. After removing the excess of P.T.S. with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution, the product was extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated to expel the solvent. The residue on distillation under reduced pressure gave the ketone (XVI); b.p. 115–17°/12 mm; yield 1.5 g. (63%); η_D^{32} 1.4560 (literature¹² reports b.p. 110°/10 mm.).

(Found : C, 78.63; H, 10.41. Calc'd for $C_{10}H_{16}O$: C, 78.89; H, 10.59%). The ketone was characterised by comparing its characteristic absorption peaks at 3050 cm^{-1} (olefinic double bond), 1705 cm^{-1} (–C = O), 1605 cm^{-1} (conj. double bond), 995 and 905 cm^{-1} (vinyl) with those reported in literature¹².

2-Methyl-6-methylene-7-octen-4-ol (VIII) : To an ice-cooled solution of the ketone (XVI, 1.35 g.) in methyl alcohol (40 ml.) and water (10 ml.) was added sodium borohydride (1 g.) and the solution was stirred at 0° for 3 hrs. Thereafter the reaction mixture was

extracted thoroughly with ether. The combined ether extract was dried (Na_2SO_4), solvent removed and the residue distilled under reduced pressure to furnish the alcohol (VIII); b.p. $109-10^\circ/10$ mm; yield 1.1 g (81%); η_D^{32} 1.4785 (literature¹² reports b.p. $110^\circ/10$ mm.).

(Found : C, 77.57; H, 11.69. Calc'd for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$: C, 77.86; H, 11.76%). I.R. spectrum had bands at 3350, 3050, 2900, 1790, 1605, 1445, 1320, 1300, 1000, 905, 890 which are identical to those reported by Silverstein *et al.* U.V. spectrum had $\lambda_{max}^{methanol} = 225 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\epsilon \sim 18,000$).

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